

**MARINE
CONSERVATION
PHILIPPINES**

Beyond the reef:
Habitat-based surveys of fish and
invertebrate communities in seagrass–reef
seascapes of Zamboanguita, Philippines

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SUMMARY

Marine Conservation Philippines (MCP) has conducted regular reef monitoring in Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental, since 2017. This research project examined whether additional surveys of adjacent habitats provide useful information beyond MCP's standard reef monitoring.

Fish and invertebrate communities were surveyed across seagrass, seagrass-reef interface, and reef habitats at three MCP-monitored sites associated with marine protected areas. The main analyses used survey data collected in 2025, while comparable data from 2020 were used to assess whether broad habitat-associated patterns were maintained through time. Exploratory invertebrate night surveys were also conducted.

Habitat type was the strongest factor structuring both fish and invertebrate communities in 2025. Seagrass communities differed clearly from reef and interface communities, while interface habitats were more reef-like for fish and more transitional for invertebrates. Community composition provided the clearest evidence that adjacent seagrass and interface habitats support assemblages not fully captured by reef monitoring alone.

Broad habitat-associated patterns were generally maintained between 2020 and 2025, although temporal comparisons should be interpreted cautiously due to changes in monitoring protocols. Night surveys recorded higher abundance and additional taxa not observed during daytime surveys, suggesting that daytime-only monitoring may underrepresent nocturnal and cryptic fauna.

Overall, the results support implementing periodic or targeted surveys of adjacent seagrass and interface habitats. Habitat mapping and selected habitat-based surveys could provide valuable context for interpreting MCP's long-term reef monitoring data.

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Front page photo by the author:

Young *Diadema* sp. sea urchin in Dalakit seagrass.

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INTRODUCTION

Tropical coastal habitats often occur as mosaics of seagrass beds, sand flats, coral reefs, and other shallow-water habitats. These habitats can support different communities and ecological functions, while also being linked by animal movement, feeding relationships, and life-history changes among fish (McMahon, Berumen, and Thorrold 2012; Unsworth et al. 2008). Considering that adjacent non-reef habitats can influence reef-associated fish assemblages, monitoring and management based only on reef habitats may miss important parts of the wider coastal seascape (Abesamis 2018; Sievers et al. 2024). Seagrass and transition areas should therefore be considered when designing, implementing, and interpreting monitoring programmes for reef-associated ecosystems. This is particularly relevant for small community-managed marine protected areas (MPAs), where protected boundaries may not include all habitats used by reef-associated species.

Seagrass meadows are distinct ecosystems that support their own biological communities, including diverse macroinvertebrate assemblages influenced by seagrass structure and local environmental conditions (Alsaftar et al. 2020; Barry et al. 2021). They are also used by transient and juvenile fish, including some reef-associated species, and may form part of broader foraging seascapes for mobile fish (Honda et al. 2013; Unsworth et al. 2008). Coral reefs support highly diverse communities and provide important resources for coastal livelihoods. Between these habitat types, seagrass-reef interface areas contain both seagrass and reef substrate to varying degrees. These transition habitats may support mixed or variable assemblages from both neighbouring habitats, and should be treated as a separate habitat category where present (Campbell, Kartawijaya, and Sabarini 2011; Tuya et al. 2011).

Marine Conservation Philippines (MCP) has conducted regular reef monitoring in Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental, Philippines under the current survey protocol since 2017. The monitoring programme includes fish, invertebrates, substrate composition, and selected predation indicators, although monitoring lists have changed somewhat over time in response to external priorities and requirements. MCP's monitoring roster and the protection status of individual sites have also changed over time. Most sites monitored today are community-managed MPAs, although some non-protected sites are also monitored for comparison.

This study focuses on fish and invertebrates in three MCP-monitored MPAs, with additional surveys conducted in seagrass and interface habitats adjacent to the reefs. All three sites differ in habitat layout, habitat inclusion within MPA boundaries, depth, and protection history. These

differences provide an opportunity to compare MCP's regularly monitored reef habitats with adjacent seagrass and interface habitats that are not part of the standard monitoring programme, and to examine whether community patterns are mainly structured by habitat type, by site-level conditions, or by both.

This report builds on a related project conducted in 2020 (Westlake 2021). Because monitoring protocols and taxonomic recording categories changed between the survey periods, the 2025 data were used as the main dataset for describing current habitat-associated patterns, while the 2020 data provided a broad temporal comparison of taxa that could be compared consistently between years. The report therefore focuses on the added value of habitat-based comparisons for interpreting reef-focused monitoring data.

This report aims to:

1. Describe differences in fish and invertebrate communities across seagrass, seagrass-reef interface, and reef habitats;
2. Assess whether habitat-associated patterns are consistent across all three sites;
3. Evaluate whether broad taxonomic and feeding-group patterns were maintained between 2020 and 2025;
4. Assess whether exploratory night surveys provide additional information not captured by daytime monitoring; and
5. Identify whether adjacent seagrass and interface habitats provide useful additional information for future MCP monitoring and management.

METHODS

STUDY AREA AND SURVEY CONTEXT

Following MCP's survey protocols, fish and invertebrate abundances and size categories were recorded across different habitat types at three sites where MCP conducts regular reef monitoring: Malatapay (Maluay Malatapay MPA), Lutoban North (northern section of Lutoban Gac-Ang MPA), and Dalakit (Dalakit Poblacion MPA) (**Figure 1**). Habitats surveyed were seagrass (continuous seagrass, no reef substrate), interface (approximately 50/50 mixed seagrass and reef) and reef (continuous coral reef). Habitats were identified visually prior to transect placement. All sites are associated with community-managed marine protected areas (MPAs), although habitat inclusion within MPA boundaries varied among sites.

This report combines data from two survey periods:

- January-February 2020: surveys conducted under an earlier MCP project

- June-August 2025: repeat surveys conducted to reassess community patterns and enable comparison with the earlier dataset

Figure 1. Map showing the boundaries of Lutoban Gac-Ang, Dalakit Poblacion, and Maluay Malatapay marine protected areas (MPAs) in Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental, Philippines. The study sites referred to as ‘Lutoban North’, ‘Dalakit’, and ‘Malatapay’ correspond to these MPAs (with Lutoban North representing the northern section of Lutoban Gac-Ang MPA). Spatial data (MPA boundaries and shoreline layers) provided by Ewan Gleave (Marine Conservation Philippines); map prepared by the author.

STUDY SITES

Malatapay

Maluay Malatapay MPA was established in 2022, and covers 1.6 ha. The seagrass is mainly located outside the MPA at approximately 3 m depth, but extends down to 10 m in some areas. The interface habitat is also in shallow water, and lies predominantly outside MPA boundaries, while the reef begins in shallow water before dropping off and is relatively large compared to MPA size and the other surveyed sites.

Lutoban North

Lutoban North is the northern part of the larger Lutoban Gac-Ang MPA (15.1 ha), established in 2000. The seagrass is located in a shallow bay at 1–3 m depth, the interface zone sits at

approximately 5 m within the MPA boundaries, while the reef begins at 7 m. Major shoreline erosion and changes in seagrass extent were observed in Lutoban North between survey periods.

Dalakit

Dalakit Poblacion MPA was established in 2014 and covers 10.1 ha. The reef is relatively small and located in extremely shallow water of 0–3 m, while the extensive seagrass bed sits further out from shore and deeper than the reef (5–7 m), but inside the MPA boundaries. There is no interface zone in Dalakit, and sand flats surround the reef.

SURVEY DESIGN

Surveys followed MCP's standardised underwater visual census protocols, adapted for the habitat depth of the individual sites. These protocols divide each site into monitoring zones based on reef extent, to ensure that surveys are distributed more evenly across the reef. Malatapay and Lutoban each have three monitoring zones, while Dalakit has one. Reef monitoring within these zones is further divided into three standard depth ranges where possible: shallow (3–7 m), medium (9–13 m), and deep (15–19 m). For this study, the same monitoring-zone framework was used for seagrass, interface, and reef habitats. In 2025, some shallow reef monitoring areas at Malatapay and Lutoban North overlapped with interface habitat; these transects were therefore treated as interface samples in this report, and additional shallow reef transects were conducted at approximately 7–9 m. At Lutoban North, seagrass surveys in 2025 were conducted in only two of the three monitoring zones, as comparable seagrass habitat could not be clearly identified in the remaining zone.

Transects were 30 m x 5 m, with two divers per transect. Fish (10 min per transect) and invertebrates (30 min per transect) were surveyed separately. All target taxa or monitoring groups observed within the transect area were recorded and size-estimated. For fish surveys, a 15-minute settling period was included prior to surveying, to allow the fish to move back into the transect area following reel placement. The entire water column was observed, including behind the divers. For invertebrates, crevices and substrate surfaces were searched systematically. More transects were done at larger reefs (e.g. Malatapay and Lutoban North), with fewer at Dalakit. The number of transects varied among sites and habitats because survey effort followed MCP's monitoring design and local habitat extent. Sample sizes and surveyed depth for each year, site, habitat, and survey type are provided in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Number of daytime transects included in the report analyses by year, site, habitat, and survey type.

Year	Site	Habitat	Fish transects	Invertebrate transects	Surveyed depth (m)	
2025	Malatapay	Seagrass	6	6	3–6	
		Interface	7	6	4–8	
		Reef	22	22	5–19	
	Lutoban N	Seagrass	4	7	1–3	
		Interface	4	8	4–7	
		Reef	15	17	7–19	
	Dalakit	Seagrass	4	6	5–7	
		Reef	4	6	1–3	
	2020	Malatapay	Seagrass	6	6	0–7
			Interface	7	6	0–7
Reef			20	20	3–19	
Lutoban N		Seagrass	4	7	0–7	
		Interface	4	8	0–7	
		Reef	12	18	3–19	
Dalakit		Seagrass	4	6	5–7	
		Reef	5	6	2–4	

Exploratory night surveys

In addition to daytime surveys, a total of three invertebrate night survey transects were conducted in the seagrass habitat at Dalakit in each year. These surveys followed the same transect approach as daytime surveys, using dive torches for illumination. They were conducted to assess whether daytime monitoring underestimates nocturnally active invertebrate communities, and data were analysed separately from the main dataset. Considering the limited number of surveys, the results are treated as exploratory.

DATA PROCESSING

Due to differences in monitoring protocols between years, two datasets were constructed. The primary dataset consisted of the surveys conducted in 2025. It included taxa recorded under the current MCP monitoring protocol and was used to describe present-day habitat patterns. As MCP monitors some bottom-dwelling fish, such as porcupinefish and pipefish, under the invertebrate protocol, while squid and turtles are included in fish surveys, these taxa were retained in their respective monitoring categories. For simplicity, these datasets are still referred to as “invertebrates” and “fish” throughout the report, although they include some taxa outside these groups. Feeding-group analyses remained restricted to taxonomically appropriate groups, as feeding-group classifications were defined separately for fish and invertebrates and are not directly transferable across those groups. For fish diversity and community composition analyses, records were grouped to shared taxonomic or monitoring-group levels where necessary. This was done to make comparisons more consistent and reduce bias caused by differences in taxonomic resolution, as only some fish are recorded down to species level.

Scientific names, monitoring lists, taxonomic aggregation levels used for fish, and feeding-group classifications are provided in the **Appendices**. In the main text, common names or MCP monitoring-group names are used for readability.

Temporal comparisons between 2020 and 2025 used filtered datasets restricted to taxa or monitoring groups recorded consistently across both years (see **Appendix D**). This reduced bias caused by changes in monitoring protocols and taxonomic resolution.

Large single-transect aggregations that disproportionately dominated relative composition were excluded from descriptive taxa-composition figures where they obscured broader habitat patterns. These exclusions were made only for descriptive visual summaries and are noted in the relevant results sections or figure captions.

STATISTICAL ANALYSES

All analyses were conducted in R. Statistical tests were selected according to the data structure and assumptions of each analysis, as described below.

Diversity

Taxonomic diversity was calculated for each transect using Simpson’s Diversity Index. This index gives a measure of how diverse each transect was, taking into account both the number of taxa recorded and how evenly individuals were distributed among them.

Diversity was first calculated separately for each transect, and then averaged for each combination of site and habitat. This avoided bias that can occur if all individuals are pooled before calculating diversity, as pooled data can overemphasise samples with especially high abundance.

For 2025 data, diversity was compared among habitats, sites, and site × habitat combinations using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with Habitat and Site included as fixed factors and including a Habitat × Site interaction term. Normality was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk tests, and homogeneity of variance was assessed using Levene's tests. Where significant effects were detected, Tukey's HSD post-hoc tests were used to identify which groups differed.

Comparisons between 2020 and 2025 were carried out separately for each site. This was done because the sites differed in habitat structure, protection history, and monitoring context, meaning that pooling sites could obscure local patterns. Where appropriate, two-way ANOVA was used to test for overall effects of Year, Habitat, and their interaction. Wilcoxon rank-sum tests were used for separate year-to-year comparisons within individual habitats.

Community composition analyses

Community composition was analysed to assess whether fish and invertebrate assemblages differed among habitats and sites. Analyses were based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity, which compares transects using both taxon identity and abundance.

Patterns were visualised using ordination plots, where transects with more similar communities appear closer together and more different communities appear farther apart. Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) was used for fish communities and non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) for invertebrate communities, as these methods provided the clearest and most interpretable representations for the respective datasets.

Differences in community composition were tested using permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Site, Habitat, and their interaction were included as predictors, and significance was assessed using permutation tests. Additional within-site PERMANOVAs were conducted to test whether habitat differences remained significant within each site.

Multivariate dispersion was also assessed to check whether apparent community differences could be partly explained by differences in variability within groups. Differences in dispersion were assessed for Site and Habitat groupings using analysis of variance on distances to group centroids.

Taxa composition and habitat association analyses

To support interpretation of the statistical community composition analyses, additional descriptive analyses were carried out to identify which taxa or monitoring groups contributed most to the observed habitat patterns. Unlike the diversity and multivariate fish analyses, descriptive composition figures were shown at MCP monitoring level to improve interpretability for management and monitoring purposes.

Habitat associations were assessed descriptively by comparing the distribution and abundance of taxa across seagrass, interface, and reef habitats. These analyses were intended to complement the formal statistical tests by showing which taxa or monitoring groups were driving the broader community patterns.

The exploratory night survey data were analysed in the same general way, comparing day and night samples rather than years to identify taxa more strongly associated with daytime or nighttime surveys. Formal day-night statistical comparisons were conducted for the 2025 dataset only; 2020 night survey patterns were summarised descriptively.

Feeding-group analyses

Feeding-group analyses were used to examine whether habitats and sites differed in the ecological roles represented by their fish and invertebrate communities. Taxa were grouped into feeding-group categories based on their main feeding strategies, and the relative contribution of these groups was compared among habitats and sites using abundance-based analyses.

Differences in overall feeding-group composition among habitats and sites were tested using PERMANOVA based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Where relevant, pairwise post-hoc comparisons were conducted using permutation-based multivariate tests.

Differences in individual feeding-group abundances and feeding-group diversity were assessed using Kruskal-Wallis tests. Feeding-group diversity was evaluated using Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index, Simpson's Diversity Index, and Pielou's Evenness Index. Where applicable, post-hoc comparisons were conducted using Dunn tests with Bonferroni correction.

Temporal differences in feeding-group composition between 2020 and 2025 were analysed separately using PERMANOVA with Year included as a predictor to assess whether the functional structure of communities changed over time. Individual feeding groups were compared between years using Kruskal-Wallis tests where appropriate.

RESULTS

FISH DIVERSITY ACROSS HABITATS AND SITES (2025)

Fish diversity showed some variation across habitats, tending to be lowest in seagrass habitats and highest on reefs, with interface habitats falling in between (**Figure 2**). However, these differences were not statistically significant overall.

Figure 2. Mean fish diversity (Simpson's Diversity Index \pm standard error) across seagrass, interface, and reef habitats in 2025. Diversity tended to increase from seagrass to reef habitats, although differences among habitats were not statistically significant.

In contrast, diversity differed clearly between sites. Malatapay supported the highest fish diversity overall, while both Lutoban North and Dalakit showed lower values. Differences between Malatapay and the other two sites were statistically significant, while Lutoban North and Dalakit did not differ from each other.

The effect of habitat also varied between sites, meaning that habitat-related patterns were not the same everywhere. For example, reef habitats supported higher diversity at some sites, while differences between habitats were smaller or less consistent at others. This site-specific variation is reflected in the spread of values shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Mean fish diversity (Simpson's Diversity Index \pm standard error) across habitats for each site in 2025. Differences among habitats varied between sites, with no consistent pattern across all sites.

INVERTEBRATE DIVERSITY ACROSS HABITATS AND SITES (2025)

Invertebrate diversity differed clearly across habitats in 2025. Reef habitats supported the highest diversity, and were significantly more diverse than both seagrass and interface habitats. In contrast, seagrass and interface habitats showed similar diversity levels and did not differ from each other (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Mean invertebrate diversity (Simpson's Diversity Index \pm standard error) across seagrass, interface, and reef habitats in 2025. Reef habitats supported significantly higher diversity than both seagrass and interface habitats (**, $p < 0.01$).

Diversity also varied between sites. Differences were most pronounced between Lutoban North and Dalakit, with Dalakit generally supporting higher invertebrate diversity. Differences involving Malatapay were less clear and not statistically significant.

Unlike fish, invertebrate habitat patterns were broadly consistent across sites (**Figure 5**). The interaction between habitat and site was not significant, indicating that the tendency for reef habitats to support higher diversity was broadly similar across sites.

Figure 5. Mean invertebrate diversity (Simpson's Diversity Index \pm standard error) across habitats for each site in 2025. Reef habitats generally showed higher diversity than seagrass and interface habitats across sites.

COMMUNITY COMPOSITION ACROSS HABITATS AND SITES (2025)

Clear differences in community composition were observed across habitats and sites in 2025 for both the fish and invertebrate datasets.

For fish, habitat type was the main factor shaping communities, accounting for about 32% of the variation, while differences between sites explained around 11%. Although both were important, habitat had a much stronger influence. There was also a smaller but significant interaction between site and habitat (about 8%), indicating that habitat patterns varied somewhat between sites.

Invertebrate communities showed a similar overall pattern. Habitat explained about 22% of the variation, while site accounted for around 10%. As for fish, habitat had a stronger influence than site, and a significant interaction between site and habitat (about 10%) indicates that the way habitats differed was not identical across sites.

The ordination plots support these results. For both fish (**Figure 6**) and invertebrates (**Figure 7**), seagrass communities were clearly separated from the other habitats. For fish, reef and interface communities showed substantial overlap, indicating that these habitats supported relatively similar assemblages, with interface communities not forming a distinct intermediate group. In contrast,

invertebrate communities showed clearer separation between habitats, with interface communities generally occupying positions between seagrass and reef assemblages.

Figure 6. Fish community composition across habitats and sites (2025), transect-level ordination. Ordination of fish communities based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Dashed ellipses indicate clustering by habitat. Seagrass communities were clearly separated from other habitats, while reef and interface communities showed substantial overlap. Reef communities also showed greater variability than other habitats.

Figure 7. Ordination of invertebrate community composition across habitats in 2025 based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Seagrass communities were clearly separated from reef communities, while interface assemblages generally occupied an intermediate position between seagrass and reef.

Differences in variability were also evident among sites and habitats. For fish, variability differed among both habitats and sites, with some groups showing greater spread in community composition than others. For invertebrates, variability differed among habitats but not between sites, indicating that differences in community structure are primarily associated with habitat type rather than site-level variation.

Overall, habitat-related patterns were broadly consistent across sites, although the strength of separation and within-habitat variability differed among sites.

CONSISTENCY OF HABITAT-ASSOCIATED PATTERNS ACROSS SITES (2025)

Habitat-related differences in community composition were consistently detected across all sites (Figure 8, Figure 9), although the strength and structure of these differences varied among sites.

When each site was analysed separately, habitat differences remained significant in all cases. For fish, clear differences between habitats were found within Dalakit, Lutoban North, and Malatapay. The same pattern was observed for invertebrates, with significant habitat effects within each site.

This shows that habitat type consistently structures both fish and invertebrate communities, not only across the full dataset, but also within each individual site.

Figure 8. Fish community composition across habitats within each site (2025). Site × habitat centroids derived from the PCoA ordination of fish communities based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Lines connect habitat centroids for sites with a continuous seagrass–interface–reef sequence. Dalakit habitats are shown without a connecting line due to the site’s configuration. Seagrass communities were consistently separated from the other habitats, while reef and

interface communities were more similar. The direction and magnitude of habitat-related differences varied among sites.

Figure 9. Invertebrate community composition across habitats within each site (2025). Site × habitat centroids from the NMDS ordination of invertebrate communities based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Lines connect habitat centroids for sites with a continuous seagrass–interface–reef sequence. Dalakit habitats are shown without a connecting line due to the site’s configuration. Habitat-related differences were detected in all sites, although the magnitude and direction of change varied.

TAXA COMPOSITION AND HABITAT ASSOCIATIONS (2025)

This section is intended as descriptive summaries only. As described in the methods, large single-transect aggregations were excluded to better reflect broader habitat patterns.

Fish communities

Clear differences in fish taxonomic composition were observed among seagrass, interface, and reef habitats across all sites in 2025 (Figure 10).

Seagrass fish communities were characterised by relatively diverse assemblages without strong dominance by a single taxon. However, this pattern should be interpreted alongside one notable observation from Lutoban North, where approximately 800 rabbitfish fry were recorded in a single seagrass transect. This aggregation was excluded from the relative-abundance figures as it otherwise would have dominated the figure, but it represents a biologically relevant observation. Even excluding this aggregation, most fish individuals recorded in Lutoban North seagrass in 2025 were in the smallest size class (0–5 cm), suggesting possible juvenile habitat use in that year.

Wrasses were the most consistent group across seagrass transects, with rabbitfish, trevallies, and emperors also occurring regularly. Goatfish were present at lower levels, while damselfish made only a minor contribution. Rabbitfish were relatively abundant overall, but this was partly

influenced by localised aggregations. Overall, seagrass assemblages were comparatively heterogeneous, with multiple taxa contributing to community structure.

Figure 10. Fish monitoring-group composition across habitats (2025). Relative abundance of the most common taxa recorded across seagrass, interface and reef habitats pooled across all sites. Only the most abundant taxa are shown; remaining taxa are grouped as “Other”. Large, single-occurrence aggregations excluded from this figure were 800 rabbitfish fry in Lutoban North seagrass and 72 squid in Malatapay seagrass.

Interface communities were strongly dominated by damselfish, which accounted for the large majority of individuals across sites. Secondary contributions came from sergeantfish and wrasses, with smaller contributions from barracuda, bristletooth surgeonfish, anthias, and parrotfish. Compared to seagrass, interface assemblages showed stronger dominance and a clearer representation of reef-associated taxa.

Reef communities were also dominated by damselfish, but differed from interface habitats in having a substantial contribution from fusiliers, which were largely restricted to reef environments. Other important groups included wrasses, sergeantfish, snappers, bristletooth surgeonfish, with butterflyfish also consistently present. Reef assemblages showed a strong contribution of planktivorous taxa alongside damselfish dominance.

Although these patterns were consistent at the pooled habitat level, site-level differences were evident (**Figure 11**). In seagrass habitats, Lutoban North was characterised by higher relative

abundance of rabbitfish and trevallies, while Dalakit showed greater contributions from emperors and other low-abundance taxa. In reef habitats, fusiliers were more prominent at some sites, particularly Lutoban North, whereas Malatapay and Dalakit showed a broader spread of taxa. Despite these differences, the overall habitat-associated patterns remained consistent across sites.

Figure 11. Fish monitoring-group composition across habitats and sites (2025). Relative abundance of the most common taxa recorded within each habitat at Malatapay, Lutoban North, and Dalakit. Only the most abundant taxa are shown; remaining taxa are grouped as “Other”. Patterns are broadly consistent across sites, with variation in the relative contribution of dominant taxa among habitats. Large, single-occurrence aggregations excluded from this figure were 800 rabbitfish fry in Lutoban North seagrass and 72 squid in Malatapay seagrass.

Several larger, highly mobile, or rarely recorded taxa were observed only once or in low numbers, including green turtles, pelagic fish, unicornfish, scad, and squid. These observations contributed little to overall community composition and are treated as incidental to the main habitat-associated patterns.

Overall, fish assemblages showed clear habitat-associated differences. Seagrass habitats supported more mixed assemblages, while interface and reef habitats were more strongly dominated by reef-associated groups, particularly damselfish. Reef habitats were further distinguished by a stronger contribution from fusiliers, whereas interface habitats were more similar to reef than seagrass communities in terms of dominant taxa.

Invertebrate communities

Clear differences in invertebrate taxonomic composition were observed among seagrass, interface, and reef habitats across all sites in 2025 (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Invertebrate taxonomic composition across habitats (2025). Relative abundance of the most common invertebrate and benthic fish taxa recorded in seagrass, interface, and reef habitats pooled across all sites. Only the most abundant taxa are shown; remaining taxa are grouped as “Other”.

Seagrass invertebrate communities were comparatively heterogeneous and were not dominated by a single taxon across all sites. At the pooled habitat level, sea stars were the most abundant group, followed by cone snails, collector urchins, conches and scallops. However, this pooled pattern masked strong site-level differences. At Lutoban North, seagrass assemblages were strongly dominated by sea stars and collector urchins, whereas Dalakit seagrass was characterised more by cone snails, conches and scallops. Malatapay seagrass contained relatively few individuals overall and a larger proportion of low-abundance taxa grouped as “Other” (e.g. banded coral shrimp, nudibranchs, and scattered occurrences of additional gastropods and echinoderms). Overall, seagrass assemblages were relatively diverse and patchy, with composition varying substantially among sites (**Figure 13**).

Interface communities were strongly dominated by diadema urchins, which accounted for the large majority of individuals across sites. Secondary contributions came from sea stars and nudibranchs, while banded coral shrimp and cone snails were present at lower relative abundances. This pattern was consistent across the two interface sites, although Lutoban North showed

especially strong diadema urchin dominance. Compared to seagrass habitats, interface assemblages showed much stronger dominance and lower evenness, with most other taxa contributing only small proportions to overall composition.

Reef communities were also dominated by diadema urchins, but differed from interface habitats in having stronger secondary contributions from nudibranchs and sea stars. Cone snails and lionfish were also important at the pooled habitat level. Site-level patterns varied, with nudibranchs and lionfish especially prominent at Malatapay reef, while Lutoban North reef was more strongly dominated by diadema urchins. Dalakit reef contained broader spread of lower-abundance taxa, reflected in a relatively large “Other” category (e.g. banded coral shrimp, conches, scallops, and additional low-frequency molluscs and echinoderms). Overall, reef assemblages were strongly structured by diadema urchins, but with more visible contributions from additional taxa than in interface habitats.

Figure 13. Invertebrate taxonomic composition across habitats and sites (2025). Relative abundance of the most common invertebrate and benthic fish taxa within each habitat at Malatapay, Lutoban North, and Dalakit. Only the most abundant taxa are shown; remaining taxa are grouped as “Other”. Habitat-related patterns are consistent across sites, although the relative contribution of dominant taxa and the proportion of low-abundance taxa vary.

Several additional molluscs, crustaceans, echinoderms, and benthic fish were recorded only once or in very few transects. These low-frequency observations contributed little to overall composition and are considered incidental to the main habitat-associated patterns described here.

Overall, invertebrate assemblages also showed clear habitat-associated differences. Seagrass habitats supported more heterogeneous assemblages, while interface and reef habitats were strongly

structured by diadema urchins. Reef habitats showed broader secondary contributions from other taxa, whereas interface communities were more strongly dominated by a single group.

FEEDING-GROUP COMPOSITION ACROSS HABITATS (2025)

Fish communities

This dataset does not include non-fish taxa. Fish feeding composition showed some differences across habitats, although patterns were not strongly defined.

Seagrass habitats were generally dominated by omnivores, with only small contributions from other feeding groups. Reef habitats showed a more mixed feeding structure, with higher representation of carnivores, planktivores, and herbivores in some sites. Interface habitats were variable, ranging from strongly omnivore-dominated at Malatapay to a more even mix of omnivores and carnivores at Lutoban North (**Figure 14**).

Despite these visible differences, statistical support for habitat- or site-level patterns was weak. Pairwise comparisons showed no significant differences in feeding-group composition between individual habitats or between sites. Individual feeding groups also did not differ significantly by habitat or site. One feeding-group diversity metric, Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index, differed among habitats, but this pattern was not supported by Simpson's Diversity Index or Pielou's evenness. Overall, these results suggest that fish feeding-group structure showed visible habitat-related variation, but did not represent a strong or consistent shift across habitats or sites.

Figure 14. Relative contribution of fish feeding groups across habitats within each site in 2025. Seagrass habitats were dominated by omnivores, while reef habitats showed a more mixed feeding-group structure. Interface habitats varied among sites. Visible patterns did not correspond to consistent statistical differences between habitats or sites.

Invertebrate communities

This dataset does not include benthic fish. Invertebrate feeding composition also varied across habitats, with clearer visual differences than for fish. Interface habitats were strongly dominated by grazers, while reef habitats also had high grazer abundance but included a broader mix of feeding groups. Seagrass habitats were more variable among sites, with carnivores, filter feeders, and grazers all contributing substantially in different locations (**Figure 15**).

However, statistical support for these patterns was weak. Pairwise comparisons showed no significant differences between individual habitats or between sites. One feeding-group diversity metric, Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index, differed among habitats, but this pattern was not supported by Simpson's Diversity Index or Pielou's evenness. Overall, these results suggest that habitat-related differences in invertebrate feeding structure were present visually, but were subtle, variable among transects, and did not represent a strong or consistent shift across habitats or sites.

Figure 15. Relative contribution of invertebrate feeding groups across habitats within each site in 2025. Interface habitats were strongly dominated by grazers, while reef habitats showed high grazer abundance together with a broader mix of other feeding groups. Seagrass habitats were more variable among sites. Patterns were visually different among habitats, but variability among transects was high and no consistent statistical differences were detected.

TEMPORAL PATTERNS IN DIVERSITY (2020 VS 2025)

Temporal comparisons should be interpreted with caution due to changes in monitoring protocols between years. The datasets in this section were condensed to only include taxa monitored both years, also excluding non-fish (fish dataset) and benthic fish (invertebrate dataset).

Fish diversity

Changes in diversity between 2020 and 2025 were limited and varied between sites and habitats. In Malatapay, temporal diversity was relatively stable across all habitats. The interface habitat diversity increased between years in Lutoban North, while seagrass and reef habitats showed no significant change. In Dalakit, reef diversity was broadly similar between years, while seagrass diversity was lower in 2025, although this difference was not statistically significant. Overall, changes in fish diversity were localised and inconsistent, with no clear pattern across sites or habitats (**Figure 16**).

Figure 16. Mean fish diversity (Simpson's Diversity Index \pm standard error) across habitats and sites in 2020 and 2025. Changes in diversity were limited and varied among sites and habitats, with no consistent pattern across the study area.

Invertebrate diversity

Temporal patterns in invertebrate diversity varied between sites and habitats. In Dalakit, invertebrate diversity was higher in 2025 than in 2020 across both seagrass and reef habitats. In Lutoban North, interface habitat diversity decreased significantly between years, while seagrass and reef habitats showed little change. Malatapay showed relatively stable diversity across all habitats, with no significant year-to-year differences. Overall, changes in invertebrate diversity were site- and habitat-specific, rather than showing a consistent trend across the study area (**Figure 17**).

Figure 17. Mean invertebrate diversity (Simpson's Diversity Index \pm standard error) across habitats and sites in 2020 and 2025. Temporal patterns differed among sites, with some increases in diversity observed in 2025, but no consistent trend across all habitats and sites.

TEMPORAL PATTERNS IN TAXA COMPOSITION (2020 VS 2025)

To provide a general comparison of community structure across years, taxa composition was visualised using aggregated and consistently recorded groups. These plots are intended as descriptive summaries only and should be interpreted with caution due to differences in monitoring protocols between years. Single-transect aggregations that disproportionately dominated relative composition (i.e. 800 rabbitfish fry in Lutoban North seagrass 2025 and 343 Bell's urchins in Lutoban North seagrass 2020) were excluded to better reflect broader habitat patterns.

Fish communities

Broad patterns in fish composition were consistent between years, although seagrass assemblages showed greater temporal variation than interface and reef habitats (**Figure 18**). In seagrass habitats, 2020 assemblages included larger proportions of sergeantfish and fusiliers, while 2025 assemblages showed greater representation of trevallies, rabbitfish, and emperors. Interface habitats in both years were strongly dominated by sergeantfish, with some variation in secondary taxa. In reef habitats, fusiliers were the dominant group in both years and were especially prominent in 2025. Other taxa were present at lower and broadly comparable levels across years.

Figure 18. Fish taxonomic composition across habitats in 2020 and 2025. Relative abundance of consistently recorded fish taxa or monitoring groups in seagrass, interface, and reef habitats. Taxa were aggregated to monitoring groups comparable across years; remaining low-abundance taxa are grouped as “Other”. Large single-transect aggregations were excluded where they disproportionately dominated relative composition. Broad habitat-associated patterns were maintained between years, although seagrass assemblages showed greater temporal variation than interface and reef habitats. A large, single-occurrence aggregation of 800 rabbitfish fry in Lutoban North seagrass in 2025 was excluded from this figure.

Invertebrate communities

Invertebrate composition was broadly consistent between years, particularly in interface and reef habitats (**Figure 19**). In seagrass habitats, assemblages were characterised by cone snails, sea stars, and sea urchins, but showed more variation in their relative abundance between years.

Interface and reef habitats were strongly dominated by diadema urchins in both years, although reef habitats showed a somewhat broader mix of secondary taxa in 2025. Overall, differences between years mainly reflected changes in relative abundance rather than major shifts in taxonomic composition.

Figure 19. Invertebrate taxonomic composition across habitats in 2020 and 2025. Relative abundance of consistently recorded invertebrate taxa or monitoring groups in seagrass, interface, and reef habitats. Taxa were aggregated to groups comparable across years; remaining low-abundance taxa are grouped as “Other”. Invertebrate composition was generally stable between years, particularly in interface and reef habitats, which remained strongly dominated by diadema urchins. A large, single-occurrence aggregation of 343 bell’s urchins in Lutoban North seagrass in 2020 was excluded from this figure.

Summary

Across both taxa groups, broad habitat-associated patterns in taxa composition were maintained between 2020 and 2025. Fish assemblages showed more temporal variability in seagrass habitats, while invertebrate assemblages were more stable in interface and reef habitats.

TEMPORAL PATTERNS IN FEEDING-GROUP COMPOSITION (2020 VS 2025)

Fish communities

Fish feeding composition showed visible differences between years (**Figure 20**). In 2020, several habitats showed a more mixed feeding-group structure, with higher relative abundances of herbivores, planktivores, and carnivores in some site-habitat combinations. In 2025, fish feeding composition was more strongly dominated by omnivores across several habitats and sites.

Individual feeding groups showed some significant year-to-year differences, particularly for carnivores and omnivores. However, overall feeding-group composition did not differ significantly in the PERMANOVA model, and changes were not consistent enough across all sites and habitats to indicate a clear overall shift in feeding-group structure.

Figure 20. Relative contribution of fish feeding groups across habitats within each site in 2020 (a) and 2025 (b). Fish feeding-group composition differed visibly between years, with stronger omnivore dominance in 2025 and more mixed feeding-group structure in 2020. However, patterns varied among sites and habitats, and overall feeding-group composition did not differ significantly in the PERMANOVA model.

Invertebrate communities

Invertebrate feeding composition also showed broadly similar habitat-associated patterns between 2020 and 2025, although some year-to-year variation was visible (Figure 21).

Reef and interface habitats were generally dominated by grazers in both years, while seagrass habitats showed more variable mixtures of grazers, filter feeders, carnivores and omnivores depending on site and year. Feeding-group composition did not differ significantly in the PERMANOVA model. Among individual feeding groups, filter feeders differed significantly between years, while other feeding groups showed no significant year effect. Invertebrate feeding-

group composition was therefore broadly similar between survey periods, but with some variation in the relative abundance of individual feeding groups.

Figure 21. Relative contribution of invertebrate feeding groups across habitats within each site in 2020 (a) and 2025 (b). Reef and interface habitats were generally dominated by grazers, while seagrass habitats showed more variable feeding-group composition. Patterns were similar between years, with some variation in the relative abundance of individual feeding groups.

Overall pattern

Taken together, feeding-group patterns showed some temporal variation, particularly for fish, but did not show a clear or consistent shift across all sites and habitats.

EXPLORATORY NIGHT SURVEYS (DALAKIT SEAGRASS)

Results from night surveys are exploratory and were not included in the main habitat comparisons.

Exploratory night invertebrate surveys in Dalakit seagrass in 2025 showed clear differences compared to daytime surveys. Substantially higher numbers of individuals were recorded at night (Figure 22), with total abundance significantly greater than during daytime surveys. Several taxa were observed that were not detected during daytime monitoring, including bobbit worms (*Eunice aphroditois*), bobtail squid (*Euprymna berryi*), stargazers (*Uranoscopus* sp.), dragonets (*Callionymus* sp.), and coconut octopus (*Amphioctopus marginatus*). In addition, two cuttlefish (*Sepia* sp.), a spearing mantis shrimp (*Lysiosquilla* sp.) and several more bobtail squid were observed outside the transects.

Figure 22. Total invertebrate abundance per transect during day and night surveys in Dalakit seagrass (2025). Night surveys recorded significantly higher numbers of individuals than daytime surveys. Boxes show the typical range of values (middle half of the data), the line inside each box indicates the median, vertical lines show the spread of most values, and points represent individual transects.

Night-time observations were strongly dominated by a small number of taxa, particularly conches and porcupine fish (Figure 23), which accounted for a large proportion of individuals in several transects. In contrast, daytime observations were more evenly distributed across taxa, with cone snails, scallops, sea hares, and other invertebrates occurring at lower and more comparable abundances.

Figure 23. Dalakit seagrass invertebrate composition during day- and night surveys in 2025.

Some taxa were primarily associated with daytime surveys, including sapsucking slugs, peacock mantis shrimp, sea moths, and mimic octopus, and were rarely or not observed during night surveys. This highlights clear differences in the types of organisms detected depending on time of day.

Similar patterns were observed in 2020, where night surveys also recorded taxa not detected during daytime monitoring, including bobtail squid, squid, flatworms, and cleaner shrimp, alongside a range of gastropods, particularly cone snails, with additional observations of nudibranchs and headshield slugs. However, due to differences in monitoring protocols and limited sample size, no formal analyses were conducted on the 2020 data.

Overall, these observations indicate that daytime monitoring alone is likely to underrepresent parts of the seagrass assemblage, particularly nocturnal and cryptic species, and that night surveys provide additional insight into invertebrate community composition.

INTERPRETATION AND MONITORING IMPLICATIONS

HABITAT-BASED SURVEYS ADDED INFORMATION BEYOND REEF MONITORING

This study showed that habitat was the strongest structuring factor as seagrass and interface surveys revealed communities that differ from the regularly monitored reef habitats. Fish and invertebrate composition differed clearly among habitats, and habitat type explained more variation than site identity in the 2025 analyses. Patterns were not identical at every site, but the effect on composition was still dominated by habitat type. Even though sites differed in depth, MPA history, and local configuration, habitat type remained a consistent predictor of community structure.

Seagrass communities were clearly separated from reef and interface communities in ordination plots for both fish and invertebrates. Although reef habitats supported higher invertebrate diversity, seagrass habitats supported distinct fish and invertebrate assemblages, including taxa and feeding groups that were less prominent in reef and interface habitats. This distinction is important for management because biodiversity value is not captured fully by diversity indices alone. A habitat may have lower average diversity but still contribute unique taxa, functions, or life-history stages to the wider seascape. Seagrass habitats are recognised as important habitat for reef-associated fish, including juvenile life stages (Honda et al. 2013; Unsworth et al. 2008), while also supporting diverse macroinvertebrate communities influenced by seagrass structure and local environmental conditions (Alsaffar et al. 2020; Barry et al. 2021).

Interface habitats can contain mixed or variable assemblages where structurally different habitats meet, and previous work has shown that faunal and fish assemblages may vary across reef-seagrass ecotones (Campbell et al. 2011; Tuya et al. 2011). In this study, interface habitats showed different patterns for fish and invertebrates. Fish assemblages were relatively reef-like, with substantial overlap between interface and reef fish communities. Invertebrate communities showed a more transitional pattern between seagrass and reef habitats. This suggests that interface habitats may provide particularly useful additional information for benthic invertebrate monitoring, while not always forming a clearly distinct ecological zone for all taxa groups.

Because MCP's standard monitoring focuses on reef habitats, the clear differences observed between reef, interface and seagrass communities indicate that reef monitoring alone does not fully capture the habitat-associated biodiversity of these MPA-linked seascapes (Abesamis 2018; Sievers et al. 2024; Unsworth et al. 2008). This does not necessarily mean that seagrass and interface

habitats must be monitored with the same frequency as reefs, but it does show that periodic or targeted surveys of adjacent habitats can provide important context for interpreting reef-focused monitoring results.

FEEDING-GROUP PATTERNS

Feeding-group patterns provided useful ecological context, but were weaker and less consistent than the taxonomic community patterns. Fish and invertebrate feeding composition showed some visible habitat-associated differences, but statistical support was limited and variation among transects was high. This suggests that the additional seagrass and interface surveys revealed clearer differences in which taxa were present than in the broad feeding roles represented. Feeding groups are therefore useful as a simple functional summary, but should be interpreted alongside taxonomic composition rather than used as a replacement for it.

SITE-SPECIFIC CONTEXT AND HABITAT CHANGE

Although habitat type was the strongest overall driver, site-level differences were still evident. This was expected, as the sites differ in habitat layout, depth, protection history, MPA boundary coverage, physical changes over time, and seagrass extent.

Dalakit is particularly different from the other sites: the reef is extremely shallow, the seagrass is further from shore and deeper than the reef, there is no interface habitat, and the reef and seagrass are separated by broad sand flats. This means that Dalakit does not represent a continuous seagrass-interface-reef gradient in the same way as Malatipay and Lutoban North. This is important when interpreting site-level results, as Dalakit generally supported higher invertebrate diversity than Lutoban North and also showed higher invertebrate diversity in 2025 than in 2020, while fish diversity remained broadly similar between years. These patterns should therefore be interpreted in relation to Dalakit's specific habitat configuration rather than as a simple site-wide increase or decline. Dalakit also differs from the other sites in that both the surveyed reef and seagrass habitats are located inside the MPA, making it a useful contrast to sites where adjacent seagrass habitats fall partly or entirely outside protected boundaries.

Lutoban North seagrass may have provided juvenile fish habitat in 2025, as indicated by large rabbitfish fry aggregation and many additional fish in the smallest recorded size class. This was not clearly evident in 2020. Seagrass habitats are recognised as important juvenile habitats for some reef-associated fish (Unsworth et al. 2008; Verweij et al. 2008), but the Lutoban North observation should be interpreted as site- and year-specific rather than a confirmed nursery function.

Substantial shoreline erosion and visible changes in seagrass extent were also observed between survey periods, suggesting that the shallow habitat at Lutoban North may have changed considerably over time. These habitat changes provide important context for interpreting the 2025 fish observations, although they cannot be linked directly to the juvenile-fish pattern without quantitative habitat-change data.

Malatapay provides a different type of site-specific context. Fish diversity was highest at Malatapay in 2025, and temporal diversity patterns were relatively stable across habitats for both fish and invertebrates. However, Malatapay also differs in protection history, as the 2020 surveys were conducted before MPA establishment, and much of the adjacent seagrass and interface habitat lies outside the current MPA boundary. This makes Malatapay particularly relevant for interpreting how reef-focused monitoring relates to the wider, partly unprotected habitat mosaic.

TEMPORAL COMPARISONS AND MONITORING CONSISTENCY

Temporal comparisons suggest that these broad habitat-associated patterns were maintained between survey periods. Fish composition showed some temporal variability, particularly in seagrass habitats, while invertebrate composition appeared relatively stable, especially in interface and reef habitats. However, because monitoring protocols and taxonomic recording categories differed between survey periods, the temporal dataset had lower taxonomic resolution. These results should therefore be interpreted as broad indicators of temporal consistency rather than precise estimates of ecological change. The temporal results are most useful for identifying whether major habitat-associated patterns appear robust, rather than for detecting fine-scale population trends. The survey periods also differed seasonally, so some year-to-year differences could reflect seasonal timing as well as ecological change.

EXPLORATORY NIGHT SURVEYS

The exploratory night surveys in Dalakit seagrass recorded higher abundance than daytime surveys, as well as taxa not observed during the day. Although limited in sample size, they indicate that time of day affects what is detected and that daytime-only monitoring may underrepresent seagrass-associated communities. This is consistent with other seagrass studies showing diel differences in macroinvertebrate abundance, richness, or community composition (Briones-Fourzán et al. 2020; Martin et al. 2021). Targeted night surveys could therefore be useful when biodiversity, nocturnal taxa, or cryptic taxa are a monitoring priority.

MONITORING RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these results, the following recommendations focus on preserving MCP's long-term reef-monitoring value while adding targeted habitat-level information where feasible.

PROTECT THE LONG-TERM VALUE OF THE EXISTING REEF-MONITORING DATASET

MCP's reef monitoring programme has provided a strong long-term dataset on reef-associated fish and invertebrate communities since 2017. Although monitoring priorities are not always decided by MCP and may be influenced by government requirements, tourism value, food security concerns, or other external priorities, avoidable changes to monitoring lists and protocols should be minimised where possible. Maintaining consistency in taxonomic recording categories and survey design will help preserve the long-term value of the existing dataset and improve comparability between future survey periods.

TARGETED HABITAT ADDITIONS

Prioritise periodic seagrass surveys at selected sites

Seagrass surveys should be considered where seagrass habitats are adjacent to monitored reefs, extensive, changing, or partly outside MPA boundaries. These surveys do not need to be conducted as frequently as reef monitoring, but periodic or project-based surveys would provide useful context for interpreting reef-focused monitoring results. Additional seagrass surveys should include comparable effort for both fish and invertebrates.

Use interface surveys selectively where interface habitat is present

Additional interface surveys may be useful where interface habitat is present and not already represented in shallow reef monitoring zones, particularly for invertebrates. However, because interface habitats did not always behave as a distinct ecological zone for all taxa groups, seagrass surveys should take precedence where time or survey effort is limited.

Consider a small day/night pilot survey for seagrass invertebrates

A small, standardised pilot programme comparing daytime and night-time surveys at selected sites or habitats could help assess how much daytime surveys underrepresent nocturnal or cryptic invertebrates. This would be most useful where nocturnal taxa, cryptic taxa, or priority monitoring categories are of particular interest.

SUPPORTING SITE INFORMATION

Develop and update habitat maps for each site

Habitat maps should show seagrass, interface and reef habitats, together with MPA boundaries and standard monitoring areas. This is particularly important because adjacent seagrass habitats may fall partly or entirely outside MPA boundaries, which can reduce protection of the wider habitat mosaic even where the reef itself is protected (Abesamis 2018; Weeks 2017). More broadly, ecological connectivity remains inconsistently incorporated into MPA design (Balbar and Metaxas 2019), supporting the value of practical site-level tools such as habitat maps. Where existing shallow reef monitoring zones overlap with interface habitat, such as at Malatapay and Lutoban North, these should be marked as “interface” in the database while still retaining their original monitoring-zone information.

Record simple habitat-condition notes during selected surveys

Future monitoring, especially at Lutoban North and other sites where shallow habitats may be changing, should include basic notes on shoreline change, sedimentation, and seagrass extent. Periodically updating habitat maps would support interpretation of biological differences between years and help track changes in shorelines and habitat extent.

CONCLUSIONS

MCP’s current reef monitoring protocols provide a strong long-term basis for assessing reef-associated fish and invertebrate communities. However, the additional seagrass and interface surveys done in 2020 and 2025 showed that adjacent habitats support distinct assemblages that are not fully captured by reef monitoring alone. Habitat type was the strongest structuring factor for both fish and invertebrate communities, indicating that reef, seagrass, and interface habitats should be interpreted as complementary parts of the wider MPA-linked seascape. The results also show that community composition provided more useful habitat-level information than diversity measures alone.

The results do not suggest that seagrass and interface habitats need to be monitored with the same frequency as reefs at all sites. Instead, periodic or targeted habitat-based surveys, supported by habitat mapping and consistent taxonomic categories, would provide valuable context for interpreting reef-focused monitoring results. This is particularly relevant where seagrass or interface

habitats fall partly or fully outside MPA boundaries, where habitat extent is changing, or where juvenile, nocturnal, or cryptic communities are of management interest.

Overall, incorporating adjacent habitats into selected mapping and monitoring efforts would improve MCP's ability to interpret biodiversity patterns at each site and strengthen the ecological context of its long-term reef monitoring programme. These additions may be particularly suitable as stand-alone or repeat student and research internship projects, allowing MCP to build habitat-level knowledge without immediately expanding the core long-term monitoring programme.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: 2025 MONITORING LISTS

Table A 1. MCP fish monitoring taxa/groups included in the 2025 dataset.

Common Name	Taxonomic identification	Family
Blue-Spine Unicornfish	<i>Naso unicornis</i>	Acanthuridae
Bristletooth	<i>Ctenochaetus</i> spp.	Acanthuridae
Brush-tail Tang	<i>Zebrasoma scopas</i>	Acanthuridae
Orange-Spine Unicornfish	<i>Naso lituratus</i>	Acanthuridae
Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus</i> spp.	Acanthuridae
Unicornfish	<i>Naso</i> spp.	Acanthuridae
Whitetail Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus thompsoni</i>	Acanthuridae
Yellowmask Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae
Redtooth Triggerfish	<i>Odonus niger</i>	Balistidae
Titan Triggerfish	<i>Balistoides viridescens</i>	Balistidae
Triggerfish	Balistidae	Balistidae
Needlefish	Belonidae	Belonidae
Fusiliers	Caesionidae	Caesionidae
Scad	Carangidae	Carangidae
Trevally	Carangidae	Carangidae
Butterflyfish	<i>Chaetodontidae</i>	Chaetodontidae
Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Cheloniidae
Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Cheloniidae
Snake	Elapidae	Elapidae
Shark	Elasmobranchii	Elasmobranchii
Spadefish	Ephippidae	Ephippidae
Sweetlips	Haemulidae	Haemulidae
Soldierfish	Myripristinae	Holocentridae
Cleaner Wrasse	<i>Labrioides dimidiatus</i> , <i>Labroides bicolor</i>	Labridae
Humphead Wrasse	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	Labridae
Wrasse	Labridae	Labridae
Emperor	Lethrinidae	Lethrinidae
Longface Emperor	<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i>	Lethrinidae
Snapper	Lutjanidae	Lutjanidae
Devil Ray	Mobulidae	Mobulidae
Squid	<i>Idiosepiidae</i> , <i>Lolginidae</i>	Mollusca
Goatfish	Mullidae	Mullidae
Spotted Eagle Ray	<i>Aetobatus narinari</i>	Myliobatidae
Bream	Nemipteridae	Nemipteridae
Angelfish	Pomacanthidae	Pomacanthidae
Bicolor Angelfish	<i>Centropyge bicolor</i>	Pomacanthidae
Keyhole Angelfish	<i>Centropyge tibicen</i>	Pomacanthidae
Midnight Angelfish	<i>Centropyge nox</i>	Pomacanthidae
Pearl-Scaled Angelfish	<i>Centropyge vroliki</i>	Pomacanthidae
Damselfish	Pomacentridae	Pomacentridae
Sergeantfish	<i>Abudefduf</i> spp.	Pomacentridae
Big Eye	Priacanthidae	Priacanthidae
Bumphead Parrotfish	<i>Bolbometopon muricatum</i>	Scaridae
Parrotfish	Scaridae	Scaridae
Raggedtooth Parrotfish	<i>Calotomus spinidens</i>	Scaridae
Stareye Parrotfish	<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Scaridae
Long-Jawed Mackerel	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i>	Scombridae
Tuna	Scombridae	Scombridae
Anthias	Serranidae	Serranidae
Barramundi Grouper	<i>Cromileptes altivelis</i>	Serranidae
Brown-Marbled Grouper	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i>	Serranidae
Grouper	Serranidae	Serranidae
Rabbitfish	Siganidae	Siganidae
Barracuda	Sphyraenidae	Sphyraenidae
Pufferfish	Tetraodontidae	Tetraodontidae
Whitespotted Pufferfish	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae
Moorish Idol	<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae

Table A 2. MCP invertebrate monitoring taxa/groups included in the 2025 dataset.

Common Name	Taxonomic identification / monitoring definition	Phylum
Banded Coral Shrimp	<i>Stenopus hispidus</i>	Arthropoda
Harlequin Shrimp	<i>Hymenocera elegans</i>	Arthropoda
Lobster	Nephropidae, Palinuridae, Scyllaridae	Arthropoda
Mantis Shrimp	<i>Lysiosquilla maculata</i> , <i>Odontodactylus scyllarus</i>	Arthropoda
Other Cleaner Shrimp	Lysmatidae, Palaemonidae, Stenopodidae	Arthropoda
Other Crab	Xanthidae, Brachyura >5cm (excluding Box Crabs, Decorator Crabs, Hermit Crabs and Swimming Crabs)	Arthropoda
Other Shrimp	Penaeidae >5cm (excluding Other Cleaner Shrimp and any species monitored separately)	Arthropoda
Blue-Spotted Stingray	<i>Taeniura lymna</i>	Chordata
Eel	Muraenidae, Ophichtidae	Chordata
Frogfish	Antennariidae	Chordata
Lionfish	Scorpaenidae	Chordata
Pipefish	Syngnathidae	Chordata
Porcupinefish	Didontidae	Chordata
Ribbon Eel	Muraenidae	Chordata
Scorpionfish	Scorpaenidae	Chordata
Sea Horse	Syngnathidae	Chordata
Amberfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Theleota anax</i>	Echinodermata
Blackspotted Sea Cucumber	<i>Pearsonothuria graeffei</i>	Echinodermata
Collector Urchin	<i>Triploneustes gratilla</i>	Echinodermata
Cushion Star	<i>Culcita novaeguineae</i>	Echinodermata
Diadema Urchin	<i>Diadema</i> spp.	Echinodermata
Golden Sandfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria lessoni</i>	Echinodermata
Leopard Sea Cucumber	<i>Bobadschia argus</i>	Echinodermata
Magnum Sea Cucumber	<i>Neothyonidium</i> spp.	Echinodermata
Other Sea Cucumber	Holothuriidae, Phylloporidae, Stichopodidae, (excluding Synaptic Sea Cucumbers)	Echinodermata
Other Urchin	All other Echinothuriidae (excluding any species monitored separately)	Echinodermata
Pineapple Sea Cucumber	<i>Theleota ananas</i>	Echinodermata
Pinkfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria edulis</i>	Echinodermata
Rock Boring Urchin	<i>Echinometra mathaei</i> , <i>Echinostrephus aciculatus</i>	Echinodermata
Sea Star	Echinasteridae	Echinodermata
Volcano Sea Cucumber	<i>Stichopus herrmanni</i>	Echinodermata
Blue-Ringed Octopus	<i>Hapalochlaena</i> spp.	Mollusca
Boring Giant Clam	<i>Tridacna crocea</i>	Mollusca
Common Egg Cowrie	<i>Ovula ovum</i>	Mollusca
Cone Shell	Conidae	Mollusca
Flamboyant Cuttlefish	<i>Metasepia pfefferi</i>	Mollusca
Giant Clam	<i>Tridacna</i> spp. (except <i>T. crocea</i>)	Mollusca
Giant Turban	<i>Turbo marmoratus</i>	Mollusca
Headshield Slug	Cephalaspidea	Mollusca
Honeycomb Oyster	<i>Hyotissa hyotis</i>	Mollusca
Horned Helmet	<i>Cassia cornuta</i>	Mollusca
Nilo Topshell	<i>Trochus niloticus</i>	Mollusca
Nudibranch	<i>Nudibranchia</i>	Mollusca
Other Bivalve	Bivalvia >5cm (must be accessible and excluding any species monitored separately)	Mollusca
Other Conch	Strombidae	Mollusca
Other Cowrie	Cypraeidae	Mollusca
Other Cuttlefish	<i>Sepia</i> spp. (excluding <i>S. bandensis</i> and <i>S. latimanus</i>), <i>Abdopus aculeatus</i>	Mollusca
Other Shell	Gastropoda > 5cm (excluding any species monitored separately)	Mollusca
Other Topshell	Tegulidae (excluding Nilo Topshell)	Mollusca
Other Turban	All other Turbinidae (excluding giant Turban)	Mollusca
Pearl Oyster	<i>Pinctada</i> spp.	Mollusca
Pen Oyster	<i>Atrina vexillum</i>	Mollusca
Pleurobranch	<i>Pleurobranchus</i> spp., Pleurobranchidae	Mollusca
Sap-Sucking Slugs	<i>Costasiellidae</i> , <i>Hermacidae</i> , <i>Limapontiidae</i> , <i>Plakobranchidae</i> , <i>Platybedylidae</i>	Mollusca
Scallop	<i>Anadara</i> spp., <i>Pectinidae</i>	Mollusca
Scorpion Spider Conch	<i>Harpago chiragra</i> , <i>Lambis</i> spp.	Mollusca
Thorny Oyster	<i>Spondylus</i> spp.	Mollusca
Tiger Cowrie	<i>Cypraea tigris</i>	Mollusca
Triton Shell	<i>Charonia tritonis</i>	Mollusca
Flatworm	Polycladida	Platyhelminthes

APPENDIX B: 2020 MONITORING LISTS

Table B 1. MCP fish monitoring taxalgroups included in the 2020 dataset.

Common Name	Species	Family
Blue-Spine Unicornfish	<i>Naso unicornis</i>	Acanthuridae
Bristletooth	<i>Ctenochaetus</i> spp.	Acanthuridae
Brushtail Tang	<i>Zebrasoma scopas</i>	Acanthuridae
Dark Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus nubilus</i>	Acanthuridae
Orange-Spine Unicornfish	<i>Naso lituratus</i>	Acanthuridae
Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus</i> spp.	Acanthuridae
Unicornfish	<i>Naso</i> spp.	Acanthuridae
Whitetail Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus thompsoni</i>	Acanthuridae
Redtooth Triggerfish	<i>Odonus niger</i>	Balistidae
Titan Triggerfish	<i>Balistoides viridescens</i>	Balistidae
Triggerfish	Balistidae	Balistidae
Crocodile Needlefish	<i>Tylosurus crocodilus</i>	Belonidae
Fusiliers	Caesionidae	Caesionidae
Bluefin Trevally	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Carangidae
Rainbow Runner	<i>Elagatis bipinnulatus</i>	Carangidae
Scad	Carangidae	Carangidae
Trevally	Carangidae	Carangidae
Butterflyfish	Chaetodontidae	Chaetodontidae
Porcupinefish	Diodontidae	Diodontidae
Spadefish	Ephippidae	Ephippidae
Cornetfish	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae
Sweetlips	Haemulidae	Haemulidae
Soldierfish	Myripristinae	Holocentridae
Chub	Kyphosidae	Kyphosidae
Barred Thicklip Wrasse	<i>Hemigymnus fasciatus</i>	Labridae
Blackeye Thicklip Wrasse	<i>Hemigymnus melapterus</i>	Labridae
Cleaner Wrasse	<i>Labrioides dimidiatus, Labroides bicolor</i>	Labridae
Floral Wrasse	<i>Cheilinus chlorourus</i>	Labridae
Humphead Wrasse	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	Labridae
Red-Breasted Wrasse	<i>Cheilinus fasciatus</i>	Labridae
Tripletail Wrasse	<i>Cheilinus trilobatus</i>	Labridae
Emperor	Lethrinidae	Lethrinidae
Longface Emperor	<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i>	Lethrinidae
Orange-Striped Emperor	<i>Lethrinus obsoletus</i>	Lethrinidae
Ornate Emperor	<i>Lethrinus ornatus</i>	Lethrinidae
Thumbprint Emperor	<i>Lethrinus harak</i>	Lethrinidae
Blacktail Snapper	<i>Lutjanus fulvus</i>	Lutjanidae
Blubberlip Snapper	<i>Lutjanus rivulatus</i>	Lutjanidae
Checkered Snapper	<i>Lutjanus decussatus</i>	Lutjanidae
Humpback Red Snapper	<i>Lutjanus gibbus</i>	Lutjanidae
Mangrove Snapper	<i>Lutjanus argentimaculatus</i>	Lutjanidae
Midnight Snapper	<i>Macolor macularis</i>	Lutjanidae
One-Spot Snapper	<i>Lutjanus monostigma</i>	Lutjanidae
Red Snapper	<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>	Lutjanidae
Schooling Snapper	<i>Lutjanus rufolineatus, Lutjanus lutjanus, Lutjanus madras</i>	Lutjanidae
Snapper	Lutjanidae	Lutjanidae
Two-Spot Snapper	<i>Lutjanus biguttatus</i>	Lutjanidae
Scrawled Filefish	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae
Mullet	Mugilidae	Mugilidae
Bicolor Goatfish	<i>Parupeneus barberinoides</i>	Mullidae
Dash-Dot Goatfish	<i>Parupeneus barberinus</i>	Mullidae
Goatfish	Mullidae	Mullidae
Yellowstripe Goatfish	<i>Mulloidichthys flavolineatus</i>	Mullidae
Bream	Nemipteridae	Nemipteridae
Humpnose Big-Eye Bream	<i>Monotaxis grandoculis</i>	Nemipteridae
Redfin Bream	<i>Monotaxis heterodon</i>	Nemipteridae
Angelfish	Pomacanthidae	Pomacanthidae
Bicolor Angelfish	<i>Centropyge bicolor</i>	Pomacanthidae
Keyhole Angelfish	<i>Centropyge tibicen</i>	Pomacanthidae
Midnight Angelfish	<i>Centropyge nox</i>	Pomacanthidae
Pearl-Scaled Angelfish	<i>Centropyge vroliki</i>	Pomacanthidae
Two-Spined Angelfish	<i>Centropyge bispinosa</i>	Pomacanthidae

Sergeantfish	<i>Abudefduf</i> spp.	Pomacentridae
Bleeker's Parrotfish	<i>Chlorurus bleekeri</i>	Scaridae
Bower's Parrotfish	<i>Chlorurus bowersi</i>	Scaridae
Bullethead Parrotfish	<i>Chlorurus sordidus</i>	Scaridae
Bumphead Parrotfish	<i>Bolbometopon muricatum</i>	Scaridae
Japanese Parrotfish	<i>Chlorurus japonicus</i>	Scaridae
Parrotfish	Scaridae	Scaridae
Raggedtooth Parrotfish	<i>Calotomus spinidens</i>	Scaridae
Spotted Parrotfish	<i>Cetoscarus ocellatus</i>	Scaridae
Stareye Parrotfish	<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Scaridae
Steephead Parrotfish	<i>Chlorurus microrhinos</i>	Scaridae
Long-Jawed Mackerel	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i>	Scombridae
Mackerel	Scombridae	Scombridae
Tuna	Scombridae	Scombridae
Barramundi Cod	<i>Cromileptes altivelis</i>	Serranidae
Bluespotted Grouper	<i>Cephalopholis cyanostigma</i>	Serranidae
Brown-Marbled Grouper	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i>	Serranidae
Coral Grouper	<i>Cephalopholis miniata</i>	Serranidae
Grouper	Serranidae	Serranidae
Honeycomb Grouper	<i>Epinephelus merra</i>	Serranidae
Lyretail	<i>Variola albimarginata, Variola louti</i>	Serranidae
Peacock Grouper	<i>Cephalopholis argus</i>	Serranidae
Slender Grouper	<i>Amyperodon leucogrammicus</i>	Serranidae
Golden Rabbitfish	<i>Siganus guttatus</i>	Siganidae
Rabbitfish	Siganidae	Siganidae
Virgate Rabbitfish	<i>Siganus virgatus</i>	Siganidae
White-Spotted Rabbitfish	<i>Siganus canaliculatus</i>	Siganidae
Barracuda	Sphyraenidae	Sphyraenidae
Blackfin Barracuda	<i>Sphyraena quenie</i>	Sphyraenidae
Great Barracuda	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae
Yellowtail Barracuda	<i>Sphyraena flavicauda</i>	Sphyraenidae
Map Pufferfish	<i>Arothron mappa</i>	Tetraodontidae
Star Pufferfish	<i>Arothron stellatus</i>	Tetraodontidae

Table B 2. MCP invertebrate monitoring taxa/groups included in the 2020 dataset.

Common Name	Species	Family	Phylum
Banded Coral Shrimp	<i>Stenopus hispidus</i>	Stenopodidae	Arthropoda
Box Crab	<i>Calappa</i> spp.	Calappidae	Arthropoda
Harlequin Shrimp	<i>Hymenocera elegans</i>	Hymenoceridae	Arthropoda
Lobster	Nephropidae, Palinuridae, Scyllaridae	Nephropidae, Palinuridae, Scyllaridae	Arthropoda
Mantis Shrimp	<i>Lysiosquilla maculata</i> , <i>Odontodactylus scyllarus</i>	Lysiosquillidae, Odontodactylidae	Arthropoda
Other Cleaner Shrimp	<i>Lysmata amboinensis</i> , <i>Lysmata debelius</i> , <i>Stenopus pyronotus</i> , <i>Urocaridella</i> spp.	Lysmatidae, Palaemonidae, Stenopodidae	Arthropoda
Other Crab	Xanthidae,	Brachyura (Infraorder)	Arthropoda
Other Shrimp	Penaecidae >5cm (excluding Other Cleaner Shrimp and any species monitored separately)	Penaecidae	Arthropoda
Swimming Crab	Portunidae	Portunidae	Arthropoda
Amberfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Thelephora anax</i>	Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
Bell's Urchin	<i>Salmacis</i> spp.	Cidaridae, Temnopleuridae	Echinodermata
Black Fringed Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria leucospilota</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Blackspotted Sea Cucumber	<i>Pearsonothuria graeffei</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Brown Sandfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Bobadschia vitiensis</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Chocolate Chip Sea Cucumber	<i>Bobadschia</i> spp.	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Collector Urchin	<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>	Toxopneustidae	Echinodermata
Crown of Thorns	<i>Acanthaster planci</i>	Acanthasteridae	Echinodermata
Curryfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Stichopus vastus</i>	Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
Cushion Star	<i>Culcita novaeguineae</i>	Oreasteridae	Echinodermata
Diadema Urchin	<i>Diadema</i> spp.	Diademataidae	Echinodermata
Eye-Spotted Sea Cucumber	<i>Stichopus ocellatus</i>	Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
Fire Urchin	<i>Asthenosoma</i> spp.	Echinothuriidae	Echinodermata
Flower Urchin	<i>Toxopneustes pileolus</i>	Toxopneustidae	Echinodermata
Globe Urchin	<i>Mespila globulus</i>	Temnopleuridae	Echinodermata
Golden Sandfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria lessoni</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Greenfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Stichopus chloronotus</i>	Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
Leopard Sea Cucumber	<i>Bobadschia argus</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Lollyfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria atra</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Magnum Sea Cucumber	<i>Neothyronidium</i> spp.	Phylloporidae	Echinodermata
Other Sea Cucumber (identified and recorded as its own species)	Holothuriidae, Phylloporidae, Stichopodidae, (further identified; excluding Synaptic Sea Cucumbers)	Holothuriidae, Phylloporidae, Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
Pineapple Sea Cucumber	<i>Thelephora ananas</i>	Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
Pinkfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria edulis</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Rock Boring Urchin	<i>Echinometra mathaei</i> , <i>Echinostrephus aciculatus</i>	Echinometridae	Echinodermata
Sap-Sucking Slugs	Costasiellidae, Hermaeidae, Limapontiidae, Plakobranchidae, Platyhedylidae	Costasiellidae, Hermaeidae, Limapontiidae, Plakobranchidae, Platyhedylidae	Echinodermata
Sea Star	Echinasteridae	Echinasteridae	Echinodermata
Volcano Sea Cucumber	<i>Stichopus herrmanni</i>	Stichopodidae	Echinodermata
White Teatfish Sea Cucumber	<i>Holothuria fuscogilva</i>	Holothuriidae	Echinodermata
Abalone	<i>Haliotis</i> spp.	Haliotidae	Mollusca
Big Lip Conch	<i>Canarium</i> spp. (excluding <i>microurceus</i> , <i>mutabile</i>), <i>Conomurex</i> spp. (excluding <i>luhuanus</i>), <i>Dolomena</i> spp. (excluding <i>variabilis</i>), <i>Euprotomus</i> spp., <i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i> , <i>Strombus</i> spp.	Strombidae	Mollusca
Blue-Ringed Octopus	<i>Hapalochlaena lunulata</i> , <i>Hapalochlaena</i> spp.	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Bonnet Shell	<i>Casmaria ponderosa</i> , <i>Phalium</i> spp., <i>Semicassis bisulcata</i>	Cassidae	Mollusca
Boring Giant Clam	<i>Tridacna crocea</i>	Cardiidae	Mollusca
Broadclub Cuttlefish	<i>Sepia latimanus</i>	Sepiidae	Mollusca
Coconut Octopus	<i>Amphioctopus marginatus</i>	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Common Egg Cowrie	<i>Ovula ovum</i>	Ovulidae	Mollusca
Cone Shell	<i>Conus</i> spp.	Conidae	Mollusca
<i>Coralliophila</i>	<i>Coralliophila violacea</i>	Muricidae	Mollusca

Day Octopus	<i>Octopus cyanea</i>	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Drupella	<i>Drupella cornus</i>	Muricidae	Mollusca
Dwarf Cuttlefish	<i>Sepia bandensis</i>	Sepiidae	Mollusca
Flamboyant Cuttlefish	<i>Metasepia pfefferi</i>	Sepiidae	Mollusca
Flat Turban	<i>Angaria</i> spp.	Angariidae	Mollusca
Frog Shell	Bursidae	Bursidae	Mollusca
Giant Clam	<i>Tridacna</i> spp. (except for <i>T. crocea</i>)	Cardiidae	Mollusca
Giant Turban	<i>Turbo marmoratus</i>	Turbinidae	Mollusca
Hammer Oyster	<i>Malleus</i> spp.	Malleidae	Mollusca
Harp Shell	<i>Harpa</i> spp.	Harpidae	Mollusca
Headshield Slug	Cephalaspidea	Cephalaspidea (Order)	Mollusca
Honeycomb Oyster	<i>Hyotissa hyotis</i>	Gryphaeidae	Mollusca
Horned Helmet	<i>Cassis cornuta</i>	Cassidae	Mollusca
Mimic Conch	<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	Strombidae	Mollusca
Mimic Octopus	<i>Thaumoctopus mimicus</i>	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Moon Shell	<i>Cernina fluctuata</i> , <i>Natica</i> spp., <i>Naticarius</i> spp., <i>Polinices</i> spp., <i>Tanea</i> spp., <i>Tectonatica</i> spp.	Ampullinidae, Naticidae	Mollusca
Nilo Topshell	<i>Trochus niloticus</i>	Tegulidae	Mollusca
Nudibranch	Nudibranchia (further identified)	Nudibranchia (Order)	Mollusca
Olive Shell	<i>Olivia</i> spp.	Olividae	Mollusca
Other Bivalve	Bivalvia >5cm (must be accessible and excluding any species monitored separately)	Bivalvia (Class)	Mollusca
Other Cowrie	<i>Leporicypraea valentia</i> , <i>Lyncina vitellus</i> , <i>Talparia talpa</i> , Cypraeidae (excluding <i>Cypraea tigris</i>)	Cypraeidae	Mollusca
Other Cuttlefish	<i>Sepia</i> spp. (excluding <i>bandensis</i> and <i>latimanus</i>)	Sepiidae	Mollusca
Other Octopus	<i>Abdopus aculeatus</i> , Octopodidae (excluding any species monitored separately)	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Other Shell	Gastropoda > 5cm (excluding any species monitored separately)	Gastropoda (Class)	Mollusca
Other Topshell	<i>Tectus</i> spp., <i>Trochus</i> spp. (excluding <i>niloticus</i>)	Tegulidae	Mollusca
Pearl Oyster	<i>Pinctada</i> spp.	Pteriidae	Mollusca
Pen Oyster	<i>Atrina vexillum</i>	Pinnidae	Mollusca
Pleurobranch	<i>Pleurobranchus</i> spp., Pleurobranchidae	Pleurobranchidae	Mollusca
Rock Murex	<i>Chicoreus</i> spp.	Muricidae	Mollusca
Rocky Turban	<i>Turbo argyrostomus</i>	Turbinidae	Mollusca
Sand Murex	<i>Haustellum</i> spp., <i>Murex</i> spp.	Muricidae	Mollusca
Scallop	<i>Anadara</i> spp., Pectinidae	Arcidae, Pectinidae	Mollusca
Scorpion Spider Conch	<i>Harpago chiragra</i> , <i>Lambis</i> spp.	Strombidae	Mollusca
Sea Hare	<i>Aplysia</i> spp.	Aplysiidae	Mollusca
Small Conch	<i>Canarium microunceus</i> , <i>C. mutabile</i> , <i>Dolomena variabilis</i>	Strombidae	Mollusca
Smooth Turban	<i>Turbo petholatus</i> , <i>T. reevii</i>	Turbinidae	Mollusca
Squid	Idiosepiidae, Loliginidae	Idiosepiidae, Loliginidae	Mollusca
Starry Night Octopus	<i>Callistoctopus luteus</i>	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Thorny Oyster	<i>Spondylus</i> spp.	Spondylidae	Mollusca
Tiger Cowrie	<i>Cypraea tigris</i>	Cypraeidae	Mollusca
Triton Shell	<i>Charonia tritonis</i>	Ranellidae	Mollusca
Tun Shell	<i>Malea pomum</i> , <i>Tonna</i> spp.	Tonnidae	Mollusca
Volute Shell	<i>Cymbiola vespertilio</i>	Volutidae	Mollusca
Wonderpus Octopus	<i>Wunderpus photogenicus</i>	Octopodidae	Mollusca
Flatworm	Polycladida	Polycladida (Order)	Platyhelminthes

APPENDIX C: FISH GROUPINGS USED FOR 2025 ANALYSIS

Table C 1. Fish groupings used for 2025 diversity and community composition analyses. Groupings follow MCP monitoring categories where these differ from strict taxonomic family-level classifications. Species/groups not encountered during the 2025 surveys are not included.

Analysis group	Taxonomic grouping
Angelfish	Pomacanthidae
Anthias	Serranidae
Barracuda	Sphyraenidae
Big Eye	Priacanthidae
Bream	Nemipteridae
Butterflyfish	Chaetodontidae
Damselfish	Pomacentridae
Emperor	Lethrinidae
Fusilier	Caesionidae
Goatfish	Mullidae
Grouper	Serranidae
Long-Jawed Mackerel	Scombridae
Moorish Idol	Zanclidae
Parrotfish	Scaridae
Pufferfish	Tetraodontidae
Rabbitfish	Siganidae
Snapper	Lutjanidae
Soldierfish	Holocentridae
Surgeonfish	Acanthuridae
Sweetlips	Haemulidae
Trevally	Carangidae
Triggerfish	Balistidae
Wrasse	Labridae

APPENDIX D: GROUPS USED FOR 2020–2025 TEMPORAL COMPARISONS

Table D 1. Fish taxa or monitoring groups retained for temporal comparison between 2020 and 2025. Groups not encountered during either survey period are not included.

Analysis group	Taxonomic grouping
Angelfish	Pomacanthidae
Barracuda	Sphyraenidae
Bream	Nemipteridae
Butterflyfish	Chaetodontidae
Cleaner wrasse	<i>Labrioides dimidiatus</i> , <i>Labroides bicolor</i>
Emperor	Lethrinidae
Fusilier	Caesionidae
Goatfish	Mullidae
Grouper	Serranidae
Long-Jawed Mackerel	Scombridae
Needlefish	Belonidae
Parrotfish	Scaridae
Rabbitfish	Siganidae
Sergeantfish	<i>Abudefduf</i> spp.
Snapper	Lutjanidae
Soldierfish	Holocentridae
Spadefish	Ephippidae
Surgeonfish	Acanthuridae
Sweetlips	Haemulidae
Trevally	Carangidae
Triggerfish	Balistidae

Table D 2. Invertebrate taxa used for 2020–2025 temporal comparisons. Names are simplified from the condensed analysis dataset for readability; full monitoring definitions are provided in Appendices Table A 2 & Table B 2.

Species
Banded Coral Shrimp
Other Cleaner Shrimp
Other Shrimp
Crab
Boring Giant Clam
Giant Clam
Honeycomb Oyster
Other Bivalves
Pearl Oyster
Pen Oyster
Scallops
Thorny Oyster
Cuttlefish
Flamboyant Cuttlefish
Flatworm
Common Egg Cowrie
Cone
Giant Turban
Horned Helmet
Nilo Top
Other Conch
Other Cowrie
Other Shell
Other Top
Other Turban
Scorpion Spider Conch
Small Conch
Tiger Cowrie
Headshield Slug
Mantis Shrimp
Nudibranch
Sea Hare
Mimic Octopus
Other Octopus
Sapsucking Slug
Amberfish Sea Cucumber
Black Spotted Sea Cucumber
Leopard Sea Cucumber
Magnum Sea Cucumber
Other Sea Cucumber
Pinkfish Sea Cucumber
Volcano Sea Cucumber
Sea Cushions
Sea Stars
Collector Urchin
Diadema Urchin
Other Urchin
Rock Boring Urchin

APPENDIX E: FEEDING-GROUP CLASSIFICATIONS

Table E 1. Fish feeding-group classifications used in the feeding-group analyses. Classifications are provided for the analysis groups used in the report; detailed species and monitoring-group definitions are provided in the monitoring-list appendices (Appendix A: 2025 monitoring lists & Appendix B: 2020 monitoring lists).

Species	Feeding group
Angelfish	Omnivore
Anthias	Planktivore
Barracuda	Piscivore
Big Eye	Carnivore
Bream	Omnivore
Butterflyfish	Omnivore
Damselfish	Omnivore
Emperor	Omnivore
Flounder	Carnivore
Fusilier	Planktivore
Goatfish	Carnivore
Grouper	Carnivore
Long-Jawed Mackerel	Piscivore
Moorish Idol	Omnivore
Needlefish	Piscivore
Parrotfish	Herbivore
Pufferfish	Omnivore
Rabbitfish	Herbivore
Remora	Omnivore
Snapper	Carnivore
Soldierfish	Planktivore
Spadefish	Omnivore
Surgeonfish	Herbivore
Sweetlips	Carnivore
Trevally	Piscivore
Triggerfish	Omnivore
Unicornfish	Herbivore
Wrasse	Omnivore

Table E 2. Invertebrate feeding-group classifications used in the feeding-group analyses. Classifications are provided for the analysis groups used in the report; detailed species and monitoring-group definitions are provided in the monitoring-list appendices (Appendix A: 2025 monitoring lists & Appendix B: 2020 monitoring lists.

Species	Feeding Group
Other Cleaner Shrimp	Cleaner
Banded Coral Shrimp	Cleaner
Common Egg Cowrie	Corallivore
Sea Cucumbers	Deposit feeder
Bivalves - Clams, Oysters, Scallops	Filter feeder
Gastropods - Tops, Turbans, Conches, Other Cowries	Grazer
Sapsucking Slug	Grazer
Sea Hare	Grazer
Sea Urchins	Grazer
Crab	Omnivore
Gastropods - Other Shell	Omnivore
Gastropods - Tiger Cowrie	Omnivore
Sea Cushions	Omnivore
Other Shrimp	Omnivore
Cuttlefish	Carnivore
Flatworm	Carnivore
Gastropods - Cone, Horned Helmet, Headshield Slug	Carnivore
Mantis Shrimp	Carnivore
Nudibranch	Carnivore
Octopus	Carnivore
Sea Stars	Carnivore